

An Investigation into the Factors Responsible for Academic Stress at University Level-Policy Implications for Relevant Stakeholders

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ABSTRACT

Nature of the stressor may be physical, social, emotional and academic that can result in physical or mental disturbance and even can result in occurrence of mental diseases. Educational stress can be defined as the exposure of student with environmental stressors, the student's intellectual assessment and adopting with education-associated stressors. It includes insufficient rest, less adequate food, and deficiency of effective planning of time to utilize for study. Therefore, the present research was conducted to identify different factors responsible for academic stress of the students. The sample size determined was 143 through an online software keeping 5% confidence interval. The validity and reliability of the research instrument was ensured before final data collection. The data were collected face-to-face from the selected respondents and were analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The results revealed that financial issues and procrastination were among the significant stressors compared to other factors listed. Therefore, it was suggested that possible necessary steps should be taken by the relevant stakeholders in order to lessen the intensity of stress that will indirectly affect their academic performance.

Keywords: Educational stress, Home factors, Behavioral problems

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INTRDUCTION

University students' assessment stress has long been a topic of interest. Many factors are involved in examination stress among the students such as insufficient information's they needed, way of study they adopt and lack of preparation for assessment (Neill et al., 2018). When students experienced excessive examination stress which affect them negatively resulting in onset of anxiety among students either during or before the examination which indirectly effect their educational achievements. Educational stress can be defined as the exposure of student with environmental stressors, the student's intellectual assessment and adopting with education-associated stressors as well as the mental and physiological reactions to those stressors (Lou and Chi, 2013). A mild type of examination stress is some time beneficial for better performance of students. As when we are doing some sort of project a mild pressure force us to do a good job, and focus in a better way as compared to relaxed condition. However, when students are taken under excessive stress either before or during the examination, it can leads to mental retardation and somatic symptoms among the effected students. Nature of the stressor may be physical, chemical or emotional that can result in physical or mental disturbance and even can result in occurrence of mental diseases (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2015). Among the physical and chemical factors that can depressed the student badly includes any type of infection, trauma, toxin, and any kind of injury. Feeling tiredness, irregular pattern of sleep, keeping him or herself in isolation and feeling disturbance in stomach, restlessness, and a situation where they cannot revise the course whatever the memorized or studied are the signs and symptoms of examination stress. They get frustrated when question are there in front of them and they cannot answer those questions and their mind is totally blank (Peleg et al., 2016). It has been found that the examination stress can cause weakening and intellectual effects such as difficulties to recall and memorize the studied contents. However, there is a strong positive link has been found between the achievement inspirations and educational achievements and a significant negative relation exist between nervousness and education achievements (Nurie, 2017).

Kombo (2018) stated that various different types of phobias have been documented in different sources. People who feel excessive and unwarranted worry due to the

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expectation or presence of a particular object or event are said to be experiencing anxiety. The patient is aware that their fear is unfounded or unreasonable and that it will be challenging to get out of their suffering. Phobias that are limited to extremely particular situations, such as being near certain animals, heights, thunder, certain foods, dentists, the sight of blood, bloodshed, or damage, the fear of being exposed to certain diseases, and tests, terrify people. People who have phobias feel intense anxiety, terror, and panic. Basically, two major factors are involved in the onset of pre-examination fear or anxiety. Lifestyle is the first factor which is associated with pre-examination stress among students. It includes insufficient rest, less adequate food, and deficiency of effective planning of time to utilize for study (Chow, 2018). If a student is unable to properly schedule the time for his activities, then he can't complete his syllabus and this can result in the onset of stress. Although he has completed the whole course but due to lack of time for revision, he may suffer from stress similarly another condition that mostly students face is the feeling that he knows nothing or even forgetting each and every thing that he memorized due to limited time (Miller, 2024). Although the main cause of academic stress are academic track, admissions, students forced to change/ transfer of admission, exams, burden of extra classes, social comparison, exams stress, teachers and parents expectations (Kaur and Vadhera, 2021).

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of test stress on female students to comprehend the causes of worry during exams. Exam stress has a substantial impact on students' academic performance as well as their physical and mental well-being. In addition to parental and cultural influences, competitiveness and peer pressure are the main causes of exam stress. While common among students, it becomes problematic when students don't have enough time to focus and prepare, much like overconfident students do, which leads to subpar academic performance.

METHODOLOGY

The population of present research work was the undergraduate students of University of Agriculture who get admission in 2021 and their session fall from 2021-2025 in different post graduate disciplines of faculty of social sciences. The list of tutorial students was collected from "The Senior Tutor Office" of the University.

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The sample size determined was 143 through an online software keeping 5% confidence interval. The validity and reliability of the research instrument was ensured before final data collection. The data were collected face-to-face from the selected respondents and were analyzed through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Home Factor as the Cause of Examination Stress among Students

The emotional environment at home plays a crucial role in shaping students' responses to stress. Supportive family interactions can mitigate stress, while negative dynamics, such as conflict or lack of support, can heighten anxiety levels. The emotional environment at home plays a crucial role in shaping students' responses to stress. Supportive family interactions can mitigate stress, while negative dynamics, such as conflict or lack of support, can heighten anxiety levels (Idoko, 2018).

Home factors	Weighted score	Mean	S.D.	Rank
Lack of recreation facilities	584	4.11	0.88	1
Exhausting work	582	4.10	0.82	2
Anxiety the night before exams	576	4.06	0.83	3
Adjustment problem	573	4.04	0.80	4
Parental pressure	570	4.01	0.71	5
Low motivation from family	561	3.95	0.67	6
Negotiations	559	3.94	0.79	7
Difficulty in organizing work	554	3.90	0.77	8
Financial problem	540	3.80	0.76	9

Very low, 2. Low, 3. Moderate, 4. High, 5. Very High

Lack of recreation facilities is ranked 1st with a mean score of 4.11. This mean value falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, but it is more inclined toward the "Very High" category, indicating that the absence of recreation facilities significantly contributes to students' examination stress. Exhausting work is ranked 2nd with a mean score of 4.10. The mean score also lies between the "High" and "Very High" categories, leaning slightly more toward "Very High." This suggests

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that exhausting work is a major stressor for students during exams. Anxiety the night before exams is ranked 3rd with a mean score of 4.06. This score falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, indicating that anxiety on the night before exams is a critical factor contributing to students' stress. Adjustment problem is ranked 4th with a mean score of 4.04. The mean score lies between the "High" and "Very High" categories, indicating that adjustment issues play a significant role in elevating examination stress. Difficulty in organizing work is ranked 8th with a mean score of 3.90. The mean value falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, but it is more inclined toward "High," indicating that organizational challenges contribute notably to stress. Financial problem is ranked 9th with a mean score of 3.80. This mean score falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories but leans more toward "High." This suggests that financial issues, while still significant, are relatively lower stressors compared to other factors listed. Harlen and Deakin-Crick (2019) expressed that addressing examination stress requires a holistic approach that involves not only academic preparation but also the emotional and psychological support from families. Encouraging a balanced perspective on academic performance and fostering a nurturing home environment can significantly reduce stress levels among students during exams.

Behavioral Factor as the Cause of Examination Stress Among Students

Stress often leads to a decrease in physical activity. Many students report less engagement in sports and exercise during exam periods, which is detrimental since physical activity is known to alleviate stress and improve mood. The reduction in exercise can contribute to a cycle of increased anxiety and decreased well-being. Stress can lead to noticeable changes in behavior, including increased irritability, anxiety, and withdrawal from academic responsibilities. Some students may also exhibit changes in their academic habits, such as procrastination or disorganized studying, which can further exacerbate stress levels (Ghauri, 2021).

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Table 4.2.2: Weighted Score, Mean, Standard Deviation and Rank Order related to the Behavioral Factor as the Cause of Examination Stress among Students

Behavioral factors	Weighted score	Mean	S.D.	Rank
Learning disorder	571	4.02	0.67	1
Conduct disorder	568	4.00	0.65	2
Panic attacks	561	3.95	0.83	3
Anxiety disorder	559	3.94	0.81	4
Obesity/ More eating	538	3.79	0.77	5
Exhausting liabilities	534	3.76	0.90	6

1. Very low, 2. Low, 3. Moderate, 4. High, 5. Very High

Learning disorder is ranked 1st with a mean score of 4.02. This mean value falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, but it is more inclined toward the "Very High" category, indicating that learning disorders significantly contribute to students' examination stress. Conduct disorder is ranked 2nd with a mean score of 4.00. The mean score lies directly between the "High" and "Very High" categories, suggesting that conduct disorders are a critical factor contributing to examination stress. Panic attacks is ranked 3rd with a mean score of 3.95. This score falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, but it leans slightly more toward "High." This suggests that panic attacks are a significant stressor for students during exams. Exhausting liabilities is ranked 6th with a mean score of 3.76. The mean score falls between the "Moderate" and "High" categories, leaning slightly more toward "High," indicating that exhausting liabilities are a significant but relatively lower stressor compared to other behavioral factors listed. Kumari and Jain (2018) found that behavioral factors play a crucial role in the experience of examination stress among students. Understanding these factors is essential for developing effective interventions and support systems that can help students manage stress more effectively. By promoting healthy coping strategies, encouraging physical activity, and fostering supportive social environments, educational institutions can help mitigate the negative impacts of examination stress on student well-being and academic performance.

Moral factor as the cause of examination stress among students

Examination stress among students can be significantly influenced by moral factors, which encompass ethical considerations, personal values, and the internalized expectations that students hold regarding their academic performance. These moral dimensions can create intense pressure that contributes to stress during examination periods (Putawin and Symes, 2012).

Table 4.2.3: Weighted Score, Mean, Standard Deviation and Rank Order related to the Moral Factor as the Cause of Examination Stress among Students

Moral factors	Weighted score	Mean	S.D.	Rank
Promote negative thoughts	587	4.13	1.19	1
Promote panic attacks	581	4.09	1.17	2
Decrease self- perception skill	572	4.03	0.87	3
Develop irritation	570	4.01	0.81	4
Decrease moral skill	570	4.01	0.56	5
Leads to suicidal attempts	563	3.96	1.01	6
Reduce working memories	559	3.94	0.90	7
Interfere with attention	555	3.91	0.85	8
Cause lower performance	547	3.85	0.85	9

1. Very low, 2. Low, 3. Moderate, 4. High, 5. Very High

Promote negative thoughts is ranked 1st with a mean score of 4.13. This mean value falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, but it is more inclined toward the "Very High" category, indicating that promoting negative thoughts is a significant contributor to students' examination stress. Promote panic attacks is ranked 2nd with a mean score of 4.09. The mean score lies between the "High" and "Very High" categories, leaning more toward Very High." This suggests that promoting panic attacks is a critical factor in increasing examination stress. Decrease self-perception skill is ranked 3rd with a mean score of 4.03. This score falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, indicating that a decrease in self-perception skills plays a significant role in examination stress. Reduce working memories is ranked 7th with a mean score of 3.94. This mean value lies between the

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"High" and "Very High" categories, but it is closer to "High," suggesting that the reduction of working memories due to stress is a significant but relatively lower factor. Interfere with attention is ranked 8th with a mean score of 3.91. The mean score falls between the "High" and "Very High" categories, leaning slightly more toward "High," indicating that interference with attention due to stress is a notable concern, though not as severe as other factors. Cause lower performance is ranked 9th with a mean score of 3.85. This mean value lies between the "High" and "Very High" categories, but it is more inclined toward "High," suggesting that lower performance caused by stress is a significant issue, though ranked lowest among the moral factors listed. Carver (2017) stated that moral factors play a crucial role in shaping the experience of examination stress among students. By understanding these influences, educators and mental health professionals can develop strategies to help students navigate the moral complexities of academic life, fostering a healthier approach to learning and assessment. Encouraging open discussions about values, expectations, and ethical dilemmas can provide students with the tools they need to manage stress effectively during examinations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Decreasing the impact of home stress on education is essential for maintaining a healthy balance between personal well-being and academic success. Stress at home can interfere with concentration, motivation, and emotional stability, all of which are vital for effective learning. Therefore, it is recommended that a sustainable stable, conducive and calm home environment should be provided by the family for provision of a better foundation for learning. Poor time management often leads to procrastination, last-minute cramming, and overwhelming feelings. Therefore, it is suggested to use the **Pomodoro Technique** or similar methods to work in intervals (e.g., 25 minutes of study followed by a 5-minute break). In addition, make a to-do list with the most important or urgent tasks at the top. Learning to prioritize can reduce the feeling of being overwhelmed.

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